

TRADITIONAL SECRET CULTS AND RURAL GOVERNANCE IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Esara, Umoh Victor¹

Asuquo, Mfon Effiong²

Udoh, Anietie Jonah¹

¹Department of Sociology and Anthropology

University of Uyo, Uyo

Umohesar1@gmail.com

+2348060111898

anietieudoh2020@gmail.com

²Department of Sociology and Anthropology

Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus

mfonasuquo@aksu.edu.ng

07035490011

ABSTRACT

This study undertook a comprehensive analysis of social control mechanisms for public order in the traditional societies or nations that later became Nigeria in 1914. Ethnic groups such as Ibibio, Efik, Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, Benin, and Tiv amongst others had existed before the advent of colonialism and they had their traditional mode of governance. The study adopted a survey design the secondary method of data generation for the analysis based on information obtained. The study pointed at the traditional mechanisms which were oriented specifically to Akwa Ibom and Cross River States which such variables as Ekpo, Ekpe, Ekpri Akata, Obon, and Iban Isong were used to restore public, the court, the prison, the custom were introduced in modern societies as they relate to Nigeria. This study adopted a survey research design. 100 respondents were selected from the 9 Local Government Areas of Uyo Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State, using multiple sampling techniques, including purposive and snowball sampling techniques. Primary data were generated through interviews and participant observation from trials, convictions, and confessions, while secondary data were generated from extant literature. Both primary and secondary data were analysed descriptively. After due study, analysis and findings, the study recommended that for effective crime control to take place, there is the need to establish a coalition of key agencies such as vigilantes, job creation and special task forces should be established to checkmate both traditional and modern crime incidences. Traditional security set-up should be complemented with minimum weapons. .

KEYWORDS: Traditional Cults, Governance, Crime, Security, Social Order

INTRODUCTION

In various autonomous societies or nations that later became Nigeria in 1914, initiation into various cult groups to enforce government policies, sanctions and programmes was a common practice amongst traditionally driven governance. However, these practices predated European adventures in Africa. Traditional secret cults such as Ekpe, Ekpo, Ekpri Akata, Obon, and Iban Isong were at the forefront of traditional governance in Nigeria mostly in the 18th and 19th centuries. These traditional secret cults had long been integrated into traditional governance before the advent of colonialism. These cults were used both as political as well as religious institutions in various ethnic groups (Ekong, 2001).

Traditional cults are seen as ancestors coming to the land of the living to fight crime, deviant behaviours, social ills and oppression. It is a general belief of the people that the supernatural powers possessed by these cult groups are given to them by the gods of the land, which is why anybody behaving contrary to the norms and values of these cults must get spiritual sanction from the gods which usually result in untimely death. The initiates see traditional cultism as the spirit of the dead visiting the land of the living to guide the ways of enforcing norms and cultural values as well as checkmate the causes of sickness, untimely death and poverty. In this regard, they see these traditional secret cults as oracles of their ancestors. The non-initiates viewed these cults as blood-sucking demons that cause harm to the people and anybody who identifies with them is regarded as a wizard (Esara, 2021).

The traditional rulers do not rule all by themselves alone, especially in the area of enforcing law and order in the society, the instrument of governance was inherited in traditional cults. However, changes occurred as the legislative, judicial and executive powers were transferred from traditional cults to modern government because of civilization. Traditional cults are a force to reckon with, especially in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States. Before colonial rule took firm roots in Nigeria, some of the duties performed by these cults were the restriction of movement on sanitation days to ensure strict compliance and collection of fines and punishment of defaulters to serve as deterrence. They also administered juju (mbiam) to establish truth among conflicting parties in matters of adjudication. The traditional cults were also used in the enforcement and collection of taxes that were used in community development (Esara, 2021).

The roles played by these traditional cult groups were very functional in reducing theft, deviant behaviours, murder, and crime generally. The potency of these cult groups has helped to reduce the crime rate drastically as compared to what we are facing today in our respective communities. A careful study of these traditional cults and functions of each of the above

would reveal that the Ibibio and Efik of Akwa Ibom and Cross River States had a well-organized system of governance in pre-colonial times. The cult groups listed were available for peaceful and non-violent resolution of disputes at the individual, group, family and community levels. Traditional societies with most characteristics and functions enumerated here are found in every rural community in Nigeria (Offiong, 2003).

In some rural communities in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States, traditional cults are still very active in their respective communities despite civilization and Christianity. The traditional political authority is still in the jurisdiction of the traditional cults because no chief would be crowned without being initiated as a member of these traditional cults. Even today, among the Efik and Ibibio, no “Obong” Village Head, Clan head or Paramount Ruler can afford not to be a member of the Ekpe secret society. For, it is in Ekpe and Ekpo meetings that crucial decisions of political and social significance affecting the communities are taken. These traditional cults have the power of life and death over all members of their respective communities. The initiation rite into these traditional cults is always a remarkable day in the life of the initiates as they would be subjected to oath-taking, not to reveal the secrets of the cult to non-members. The initiate is allowed to climb a stone “Itiat Ekpe” symbolizing braveness to protect the cult, this event is usually conducted in their shrine “Efe Ekpe”. It is usually a secret ceremony because non-members are not allowed to witness this ceremony, to avoid exposure to their source of power “Mboko” (Esara, 2021). The use of traditional secret cults as instruments of social control was a common practice in pre-colonial days in the Old Calabar Province of which the present Akwa Ibom State was part until 1987 when Akwa Ibom State was created.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

When societies were governed traditionally there was a low crime rate, compared to modern governance after the superimposition of the modern governing institutions. According to Ekong (2001). The superimposition of modern governing institutions over the pre-existing traditional governing institutions has confused the direction of governance.

For years, crime control has always been advocated by different government and their agencies even when Nigeria as a nation was still under British Colonial control with its indirect rule system of administration. According to Box (2000), for some time now, Nigerian society has been plagued with frightening crimes with the attendant consequences considered to be devastating and appealing. This unsavoury development has generated a lot of concern amongst scholars, religious clerics, non-governmental organizations and government alike.

According to Clifford (2000), this concern has been expressed in the media (print and electronic), seminars, conferences and symposia, all in an attempt to meet a common ground on its control. It is understood that crime is the act of violating the law and equally is a social problem that transcends generations and mankind and characterises all known contemporary societies.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study is to examine the functions of traditional secret cults in rural governance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Specific objectives are:

- i. To examine the functions of traditional secret cults in rural governance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- ii. To investigate the traditional measures of crime control and rural governance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- iii. To suggest possible policy measures that will harmonize traditional and modern institutions of governance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Traditional secret cults remain the highest of all traditional institutions used in maintaining the moral sanctity of traditional societies Akak (2000), essentially notes that traditional methods of controlling crime and maintaining security are not of universal acceptance as it is culturally relative. For instance, some anonymous author in a traditional setting argues that he used to curse to compel people to respect their norms and values served as a social control mechanism. However, amongst the Ibibios of the south-south region of Nigeria, each lineage system is made up of several territorially kin-based units which was the source of stability and social control. But the herald of modernity has affected the kinship and extended family system and social control is no longer the same. Traditional secret cults were also used as religious institutions. Religion has also been seen as a source of strength and consolation and essential for moral education, moral endeavour and moral achievement (Akiba, 2012).

Crime Control Machinery and Governance in Traditional Society

For this study, Akwa Ibom and Cross River States were used as the basis of our study or analysis as indicated in our study method. Society however has devised ways and means of maintaining social order and dealing with those who deviate from the norms and values. Traditional cults such as Ekpe, Ekpo, Ekpri Akata, and Iban Isong served as instruments of

social control. In serious cases involving anti-social acts and law-breaking, the Ekpe and Ekpo were invited to restore order, while the Ekpri Akata dramatized the incident in folk songs to serve as a deterrent. The Ekpo and Ekpe could impose curfews to regulate the activities of people associated with troublemaking and crime. In cases of disputes between individual or groups, their decision was final. They could impose sanctions on disputing parties to restore law and order (Inyang, 1996:2). Traditional secret cults assists in no small measures in crime control and governance in these areas involved among the Ibibios and Efik of Akwa Ibom and Cross River States. It becomes imperative to explain or analyse these phenomena (Esara, 2021).

i. **Ekpo Society**

Ekpo society is a very strong traditional institution among the Ibibio and Annang people of Akwa Ibom State, their duty was to impose curfew to regulate the activities of people and ensure compliance on sanitation days. They also collected fines from defaulters and punished those who were unable to pay such fines. Fine were used in community development. Theft in the traditional society was considered a serious offence and anyone caught stealing was subjected to public disgrace, while some offenders were/are made to swear to Mbiam Ekpo “traditional concoctions” it oath which can lead to the culprit's sudden death by swelling if guilty.

ii. **Ekpe Society**

Ekpe cult was and remains the highest of all traditional institutions in the Efik kingdom, the aristocracy of Uruan and related communities in Akwa Ibom State. Ekpe was and is still an instrument of government and authority which is known as very powerful. Ekpe helps in the formulation and enforcement of traditional policies and authority. This assertion as confirmed by Oku (2000), Udo (1983) and Ekong (1983) that politically, economically, culturally and even in legislative and judicial roles cover the jurisdiction of Ekpe society or cult. Ekpe society settles major conflicts/disputes and cases involving individuals, groups and cases between different clans and other parties and sanctions as stated by Talbolt (1912).

iii. **Ekpri Akata**

This is male male-dominated and oriented group whose concern is to maintain the moral sanctity of communities. It is still known as one of the strongest forces of correction and moral cleanser in both the Efik kingdom and most communities in Akwa Ibom State. Ekpri Akata disposes of clairvoyance to all sorts of crimes and scandals committed in Efik-Ibibio communities. Merton (2000), Opines that the primary function of Ekpri Akata is the detection of anti-social behaviour, exposing those who commit such anti-social behaviour

and ridiculing them into correction. Members usually meet at night to gossip about misbehaviour and immoral acts of individuals or groups in the community. With disguised voices and sounds, members move around the village in under moral crusade and cleansing in order to ensure public order prevails.

Young girls who attempted abortion, those who stole as well as men and women found committing adultery were/and are the greatest targets and victims. They use folk songs to rebuke, ridicule and method of gossip to expose many unholy practices of members of their society/communities. In the olden days and of course up till today, Ekpri Akata was and is the mouthpiece of the public concerning secret happenings in the village. It exposed criminals, witchcraft, theft and immorality. The crusade from Ekpri Akata as of then and seldomly now was very necessary and useful as a means of getting rid of what society termed immorality, illegality and slander.

iv. **Iban Isong**

The 'Iban' group in both Efik and Ibibio were mostly relatively elderly women. Their function was aimed at sustaining discipline and repudiating immoral acts, irresponsible behaviours and utterances. They serve to protect the integrity of the women by training them in moral and domestic responsibilities and upholding the moral values/virtues of those involved. This group does not tolerate indiscriminate utterances or blackmail of the women. In extreme situations, they usually sing and dance before the offenders. They exercise unquestionable authority over the affairs of women in the community with the fundamental objective of protecting the decency of womanhood. Omagu (2000) observed that their laws are usually harsh on women who steal in the marketplaces or farms.

When caught, their hands and feet were tied and their mouth stuffed with dirt. In extreme cases, the culprit's body would be smeared with charcoal and paraded before the public. The offender could be banned from future participation in the affairs concerning women in the village and community as well. This group played a dominant role in what was referred to as the Aba Women Riot of 1929 which forced a reform, of the tax law and indirect rule system in Eastern Nigeria. The riot itself was wrongly credited to Aba when in fact it began in Ikot Abasi in 1927 and spread to other locations crystalizing in Aba in 1929 because Aba was urbanized it "stole" the show with Margaret Ekpo and other fiery anti-colonial elite-oriented women resident there in Aba then. Traditional measures of crime control and governance, we had already taken the Old Calabar Province of which the present Akwa Ibom State was part of having the same cultural similarities of almost the same replica of culture. It is necessary to state here that these groups of people have various measures of governance

and crime control and these measures suit the purpose of the time and help in the maintenance of social order in their communities (Esara, 2021).

i. **The Mbiam (Oath)**

Suspects were made to swear by “Mbiam” to ascertain their innocence or guilt. This involves oath-taking by swearing to “juju”. The effect of the oath would show up after seven days. If the suspect is guilty of the crime, its resultant effect would be the swelling of his/her body and finally result in sudden death. The “Mbiam was and is still very potent and effective in that people were scared to commit crimes in order not to be subjected to mbiam “juju”.

ii. **Rubbing of charcoal**

Theft in traditional society was and is still considered a serious offence and anyone caught stealing was subjected to public disgrace by rubbing charcoal all over the body and parading to dance stark naked across the entire community to serve as deterrence to others, thieves were also subjected to severe beating.

iii. **Banishment**

In traditional societies, people who committed serious crimes were banished or ostracized (excluded from the community by general consent). People who were sanctioned in this manner were denied access to their property and public property.

iv. **Flogging**

In traditional societies, people who violated societal norms and values were subjected to serious flogging along with other measures such as discharge and fines. Some were sanctioned to sweep community hall for a stipulated period ranging from two months to four months as the case may be.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The anomie theory was chosen to explain the causes of crime and its control measures in society. The major proponent of Anomie Theory is Emile Durkheim (1987). Other proponents of the Anomie theory are Herbert Spencer, Talcott Parsons, and Robert Merton. Emile Durkheim once posited that in primitive societies, there existed mechanical solidarity where cultural mores and folk laws controlled people's behaviours.

Today, with civilization in social control, the use of traditional cults as law enforcement agents has been replaced with modern police. According to Haralambos & Holborn (2000) as adapted from Emile Durkheim anomie is a state of lack of social norms which describes the breakdown of social bonds between individuals and amongst groups. It could represent a situation that conjures an absence of usual social or ethical standards in an

individual or group. Anomie as noted by Akak (2000) is a condition of instability and insecurity resulting from the breakdown of standards and values. Simply in our view anomie is a state of normlessness are generally happens in periods of last-paced changes when norms of existing society cannot keep up with the pace of life of normless beings. It is more like cultural lag. In the context of social control, insecurity and challenges, anomie refers to personal isolation and anxiety resulting from a lack of social control and regulation of anti-social behaviour. Anomie in traditional African society runs rampant due to several extraneous influences viz, borrowed from Western culture as expressed in what we can see when presenting modern society like build-up courts, police, prisons, internet and movies.

These persistently were not seen in African society in the olden days. These injections to a large extent dislodged the originally held beliefs and bonds that defined Africa's tenets. According to Dambazau (2002), some of these approaches have yielded more questions than answers. The lack of consensus and the controversy generated have led sociologists, historians, philosophers, legal pundits, politicians and policymakers to develop various theories for the explanation of crime and social control. Most of these ideas are tied to an existing level of knowledge of the period as interest and concern in social control date back to the earliest traces of human civilization. For instance, when people accepted the existence of witches, wizards and evil spirits, anyone who deviated from such beliefs was said to be possessed and was either stoned to death or left in the forest to die until he or she recanted. But as society got larger, more civilised and more complex, there was a shift from mechanical to organic solidarity resulting in to increase in the division of labour and heterogeneity.

The result has been that the traditional measures of social control and governance were rendered effective. Consequently, anomie and normlessness replaced the former state of solidarity. The theory clearly explains the reason crime has increased in our society.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey research design. A total of 100 respondents were selected from the 9 local government areas of Uyo Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State, using multiple sampling techniques, including purposive and snowball sampling techniques. Primary data were generated through interviews and participant observation from trials, convictions and confessions. While secondary data were generated from extant literature, both primary and secondary data collected were analysed descriptively.

RESULT

Traditional Secret Cult and Governance

Traditional secret cults have been used as law enforcement agents among various African societies before colonialism. These cults were used as political as well as religious institutions, they were used in maintaining social order in the society. One of the study participants aged 65 years explained.

In an interview with the clan Head of Oku Iboku, Ettebom Engr. Ubong Okokon said;

when society was traditionally governed there was a drastic reduction in crime as the efficacy of these traditional cults was very active as the gods of the land were visiting the land to fight against social ills and untimely deaths, he explained. (interviewed 5-2-2024)

One of the study participants in an interview aged 55 years revealed that;

most projects in the communities were executed by these traditional cults from the money collected as fines from offenders, these projects include the construction of a market, the construction of school blocks and giving scholarship support (interviewed on 5-2-2024).

In participant observation, the researcher observed that the traditional secret cults were still useful in contemporary society as they were usually displayed in public functions to entertain the public members, non-members, women and children. In an interview with Chief Isaac Eyo, aged 75 years said;

the traditional secret cults are still useful in traditional settings as they are still used as security to guide against out-of-season harvesting of crops in the community. He further said that these traditional cults are the oracle of the gods through which the community used to appease the gods of the land, (interviewed 3-2-2024).

In an interview with the woman leader Obongawan G. Bassey aged 47 years said;

that traditional cults are still useful in maintaining charcoal and parading them to dance stark naked and move around the whole community to serve as deterrence to others in the community, (interviewed 2-2-2024).

In an interview with High Chief Bassey aged 70 years, he said; that traditional cults are still very useful because, in the cases of sacrilege, they would ensure that the person(s) involved in this act were banished from the villa interviewed on 2-2-2024.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study has shown that culprits caught in any antisocial behaviour were subjected to punishment by these traditional cults to serve as a deterrent to others. According to the respondents, the findings have shown that there was equality before the law as offenders were treated in the same manner by these traditional cults without fear or favour to avoid the anger of the gods which usually resulted in mass deaths in the land. This further shows that in cases of sacrilege, such individual(s) were banished from the community by the traditional secret cults, just to guide against future occurrence. The study also showed that these traditional secret cults were used as law enforcement agents for the enforcement of social order in the land. This study showed that fines that were collected by these cults from offenders of the norms and values of the land were used in community development. The findings from the study showed that African societies were traditionally governed by these traditional secret cults before the advent of colonialism which brought about modern policing in crime fighting. Findings show that offenders were subjected to public disgrace they were paraded stark naked with charcoal rubbed all over the body to serve as deterrence to antisocial behaviour.

The study has shown that there was a drastic reduction in crime rate when society was governed traditionally through the use of traditional secret cults. It has also been shown that Africa had their traditional governance before the advent of colonialism. It has also shown that traditional cultures were used both as political as well as religious institutions among various ethnic groups including Akwa Ibom State. The paper revealed that traditional cults are still relevant in modern society, especially in the area of public entertainment where they are displayed to entertain non-initiates, women and children without any form of molestation or harassment in public. The paper also shows that it was and is a fact that traditional societies did not and still do not have written laws or codes to guide conduct as observed in Western societies, but had well-established institutions for controlling crime and maintaining social order.

CONCLUSION

This study has shown that African societies were not lawless in the pre-colonial years as they were traditionally governed by these traditional secret cults, that were used both as political as well as religious institutions among various ethnic groups that later became Nigeria in 1914. Initiation into various traditional cult groups was a common practice among the ethnic groups to maintain social order in the land before the advent of colonialism which

brought about modern policing in crime fighting and reduction. However, modern policing has taken security duty from these traditional cults, besides the machinery and mechanisms of social control that came under focus of this analysis in Akwa Ibom State. Ethnic groups in Nigeria have had to devise their social control measures, before the constitutional pervasion ones under modernization, urbanization, globalization and heterogeneous settings that post-modernity offers contemporary Nigeria and the world.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

- i. The government should create a Department of Art and Culture across all local Government Councils for them to regulate the activities of these traditional cults.
- ii. In the traditional set-up, the orthodox methods of fighting crime should be adequately complemented with modern methods of control with the help of established regulatory and enforcement agencies.
- iii. The government should allow the traditional rulers such as Elders, Chiefs, Village Heads, Clan Heads and Paramount Rulers to continue with their traditional mode of maintaining social order.

REFERENCES

- Akak, E. O. (2000). *Efiks of Old Calabar Culture and Superstition*. Calabar: Akak and Publisher.
- Akiba, L. (2012). *Nature of Crime*. Lagos: Kent Press.
- Box, S. (2000). *Recession, Crime and Punishment*. London: Macmillan Books.
- Clifford, W. (2000). *An Introduction to Africa Criminology* Nairobi: Oxford University Press.
- Dambazau, A. B. (2002). *Law and criminality in Nigeria: An analytical Discourse*. Ibadan: University Press.
- Durkheim, E. (1897). *Suicide: A Study in Sociology*. The Free Press, New York.
- Ekong, E. E. (1983). *The Sociology of the Ibibio*. Ibadan.
- Ekong, E. E. (2001). *Sociology of the Ibibio*. Modern Business Press Limited, Uyo.
- Esara, U. V. (2021) “*Cultism and rural governance in Akwa Ibom State. Focus on Itu Local Government Area*”. Dissertation submitted to the postgraduate school, University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State 2021.
- Holborn, M. (2000). *Sociology: Themes and Perspectives* (5th ed.) London: Harper-Collins Publishers Ltd.
- Inyang, J. D. (1996). *Causes and Control of Juvenile Delinquency*. A case study of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- Merton, R. K. (2000). *Contemporary Social Problems*. New York: Harcourt Brace
- Offiong, D. A. (2003). *Secret Cults in Nigeria Tertiary Institutions*. Enugu, Nigeria: Fourth Dimension Publishers.

- Oku, E. E. (2000). *The Kings and Critics of Old Calabar*. Calabar: Hope Waddel Printing Press.
- Omagu, C. (2000). *The Morality of Punishment*. London: Kegan Paul.
- Talbott, P. A. (1912). *The people of southern Nigeria*. London: Routledge.
- Udo, E. A. (1983). *Who are the Ibibio?* HCB.